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CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR TRAINING ACTIVITIES FOR ADMINISTRATIVE STAFF IN DEEMED UNIVERSITIES IN PUNE, INDIA

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Abstract:

The purpose of this paper was to explore the current status of training practices being followed in deemed universities in Pune. The way Training and Development activities for administrative staff is being considered and delivered are also discussed at length. It is also argued that how training policies and practices are important for quality of higher education in any educational Institution. The authors have looked at the challenges and problems being faced in providing training and development of non-teaching staff in Deemed Universities in Pune. The paper suggests that there is great scope for training and development policies and practices and their implementation especially in Deemed Universities in Pune.

Key Words: Training and Development, deemed universities, non-teaching staff

Introduction:

On a comparative analysis it has emerged that education is among the top priority for the developed and under-developing countries. The academicians, professionals and entrepreneurs in Higher education institutions, such as universities, colleges and polytechnics, are aware of the fact that they are labour intensive organizations; they

depend on people for the delivery of their services. A recent World Bank paper commented that "a high quality and well motivated teaching staff and a supportive professional culture are essential in building excellence" (World Bank, 1994). UNESCO has itself recognised the important role of staff in higher education by passing a Recommendation on the topic at its General Conference in Paris in November 1997.

In business and the professions there is a wide recognition that the skills of their staff need to be continually strengthened and enhanced. In the face of challenges from national and international competitors the better companies are investing more resources in the continual training and re-training of employees at all levels

The role of administrative staff in libraries, resource and computer centres is very important in academic support. The changes in new technologies require efficiency of new techniques and software in searching for information and a changed role in supporting users of these support services. The role of teachers is also becoming more and more significant in terms of providing knowledge on the domain knowledge and also grooming of students as a corporate leader, entrepreneurs and good human. Thus teachers and administrative staff are helping the student to access knowledge from all sources for attainment of common goal. Here it is pertinent to mention that in this regard the UK's Dearing Report endorsed this finding "where communications and information technology has changed the nature of learning and teaching, there is a need to review and redefine the roles of academic and support staff within institutions". Thus keeping in view of above developments the administrative staff requires new competencies such as, information technology skills, the cost awareness and sensitivity to the need for value for money, customer sensitivity, and understanding of flexible working practices as cost cutting to Management. Hence training has gain very significant tools and instrument for enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of administrative staff in educational Institutions and universities. They focus not only on the competence of their staff, but also give time to stressing the need for commitment to the organisation's goals and to promoting a capacity to change. Should not the same be true of our institutions of higher education? They are crucial to national aspirations for economic development and, if such capacity building aims are to be achieved, the institutions will have to make the most effective use of all their human resources.

According to the information available, in developing countries one of the biggest problems is acquiring and retaining the good and efficient administrative staff Hence this study is an attempt to look into various aspects of training to the administrative staff as explained in the research objective.

Research Objective:

The objectives of this study are:-

- a) To investigate the current status of training practices for administrative staff in Deemed Universities in Pune.
- b) To identify the challenges and problems being faced by them.
- c) To suggest effective measures to promote training activities for non-teaching staff in Deemed Universities in Pune.

Literature Review:

According to Flamholtz & Lacey (1981), human capital theory proposes that people's skills, experience, and knowledge are a form of capital and that returns are earned from investments made by the employer or employee to develop these attributes. The Human capital theory holds that employees should invest in specific training and further initiation of more promotion opportunities to enhance employees' career path prospects. Thus, the human capital perspective at the level of the University, due to its emphasis on skills and performance, appears to offer more support for generalized investments in the human resources.

Davenport (1999) suggests that the human capital perspective is also illustrative of the employee's point of view. He contends that employees are not costs, factors of production, or assets, but rather investors in a business. They invest their own human capital, and they expect a return on their investment. Davenport further indicates

that the predisposition for an employee to invest their time in an organization is based on sense of commitment. Nevertheless, staff development programs may be viewed as generalized investments in human capital.

Schultz (cited in Bratton) offered this definition –consider all human beings to be either innate or acquired. Every person is born with a particular set of genes, which determines his innate ability. Attributes of acquired population quality, which are valuable and can be augmented by appropriate investment, will be treated as human capita . In management terms, human capital refers to traits that people bring to the workplace-intelligence, aptitude, commitment, tacit knowledge, skills and the ability to learn. Nevertheless, the contribution of this resource to the organisation is typically variable and unpredictable (Bratton 2007:8).To achieve the organizational objectives therefore this asset must be trained.

Neglect of staff training programs as posited by Cascio (1986) leads to employers lack of opportunity to refresh the knowledge of old timers to help them learn new skills of work performance because staff training programs help employers to acquire necessary skills and knowledge required for performance in a higher job. It should also be noted that attending staff training programs might not necessarily guarantee improved employee performance. The adoption rates and the willingness to transform what is required will always determine the trend of delivery and performance.

Methodology:

In this paper qualitative methods have been used. In general, this study is conducted to understand the status of training to administrative staff and to explore the problems and challenges being faced by them towards training and development activities. The researchers have used two methods of data collection from non-teaching staff of deemed Universities in Pune, i.e. Primary and Secondary Source of data collection. Primary Data: Primary data is the original data which has been obtained first time and collected for the study being conducted by the Researcher. In this paper researcher used interview, observation and questionnaire methods for data collection. Secondary data has also been used while doing literature review through Newspapers, Magazines, Journals, Books, Websites e-journals etc.

In this study population 1353 consists of all types of the administrative staff. The questionnaire was distributed in the respective Deemed Universities 820 out of which total filled questionnaire received were 531, while analyzing the filled questionnaire 81 questionnaire were incomplete and with irrelevant information, so these 81 questionnaire stand to be cancelled. Now the total remaining 450 questionnaire stand as the sample of the study. The Authors have collected data from permanent administrative staff from Deemed Universities in Pune namely Dr. D.Y. Patil University, Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed University, Symbiosis International University, Tilak Maharashtra University, Dnyaneshwar Vidyapeeth, and Prandar Vidyapeeth.

Findings:

The findings reported in this study suggest that training have an impact on the performance of employees with regards to their jobs. This result is broadly consistent with prior management literature on training and development. In order to gain more specific knowledge of training from the sample, different questions are presented to the respondents and thus examined. These questions are focusing on employee participation in training, selection for training, methods of training and relevance of training to the work of the respondents. The above questions have been of particular interest because they facilitate an understanding of the training practice in the Deemed Universities under study. The results from the questions on employee participation in training and selection for training indicate that these Deemed

Universities have good and perhaps clear policies regarding training and development as most of the respondents indicated that they have participated in training but most of them were unaware of their selections, the plan structure, the value of participation and the outcome of the training. Many of the respondents were provided with opportunities to train under the compulsory practice of the Deemed

University which did not add value and interest to the administrative staff. In examining the question relating to the training programme quality, the results indicate that the training programmes undertaken by the Deemed

Universities are not relevant and unplanned and unsystematic as considered by the respondents' opinions. The results reveal that even though respondents have had not less than one year's service with the organization, only 133 out of the 450 out of the sample driven have ever participated in training of any kind in the organization. 317 out of the 450 who have ever participated in training do not know how they were selected for the training. The organization engages in job and refresher training and the training methods, plans, lessons, and trainers are selected as they situation demands. Training activities are largely not evaluated. Sponsorships for further studies (career development) are minimal and there is no career progression projection, nor training and development projections for individual administrative staff. This led many of the respondents to conclude, and rightly so, that training in the organization is unplanned and unsystematic. A

Discussions & Conclusions:

From the foregoing discussions, the following conclusions were drawn from the

Study:

- Deemed Universities certainly had a well-established policy to invest in the training and development of administrative staff; however the processes involved are not being duly followed.
- It also organizes training programs from time to time for its administrative staff to update their knowledge and skills and to ensure that maximum efficiency exists in Deemed Universities Pune. Administrative staff that realized the need for change in attitude and want to develop themselves
- Through formal education in order to be side by side with modern technological advances self-sponsored themselves to acquire these skills.
- Deemed universities do not have a proper planned structure of training for the administrative staff and lacks interest in improving the structure
- The awareness of the training is almost negligible and this concept has never been picked up or given more importance in the Deemed Universities especially for the administrative staff.
- Knowledge of the training practices and job performance are associated and awareness of one concept leads to the other but majority of the Deemed Universities and their administrative staffs is not aware of these two concepts and hence are not having any training program policy specially for the administrative staff.
- Majority of the respondents studied were of the opinion they want to be trained but due to the unplanned practices of training they are not getting the benefit of it.
- Training is positively related with job performance. Training opportunities like short courses, seminars, conferences, postgraduate diploma, Master degree, Ph.D programs and Vacations, which are within the context of individual control, tend to increase job performance of administrative staff in Deemed Universities in Pune have to be understood and planned in a very systematic way.
- There is need for more comprehensive opportunities for training. Promotions, both academic and administrative, followed by a clear promotion criterion, are a contributing factor towards job performance of administrative staff in Deemed Universities in Pune.
- Promoted staff can produce more quantitative and qualitative work. Their attitudes to work are improved. Demographic variables like age, gender do not play any part in training and promotions
- On the whole, the study sought to explore the relation of training on administrative staff performance and impact of performance on promotion in using Deemed Universities in Pune as a study and findings and recommendations provided. Deemed Universities at Pune will need to take action to correct its training activities, and make sure the processes involved are duly followed according to the planned and the systematic way.

Suggestions:

It is an undeniable fact that in recent times many organizations have come to the realization of the importance of the role of training and development programs as it increases the organization's staff efficiency, skills and productivity. In order to reap the full benefits of a training initiative, Deemed Universities at Pune should ensure that the following are instituted at the work place.

- Systematic Training
- Objective should be SMART and unambiguous
- Provide Specific information to administrative staff
- Career Planning and development
- Develop administrative staff through formal education
- Motivation and Morale
- Enrich job experience
- Improve interpersonal relationships
- Evaluate training for effectiveness

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